

shift social sciences and humanities for transformation and climate resilience

Gender Equality & Inclusion Plan

This document is based upon work from [COST Action SHiFT](#) (Social Sciences and Humanities for Transformation and Climate Resilience) CA21166, supported by COST (European Cooperation in Science and Technology).

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Preamble

This plan is an initiative of the Social Sciences and Humanities for Transformation and Climate Resilience CA21166 ([COST Action SHiFT](#)), supported by the European Cooperation in Science and Technology (COST). The writing process was led by Catarina Cadima (Research Centre for Territory, Transport and Environment, Faculty of Engineering, University of Porto, Portugal). With the support of Irene Christoforidi (Technological Educational Institute of Crete, Hellenic Mediterranean University), David Scott (Faculty of Social and Applied Sciences, Abertay University), and also our guest advisors: Besa Shahini (Department of Applied Statistics and Informatics Faculty of Economy, University of Tirana, Albania), Isabel Cunha (Urban Planning, Economics and Transport Laboratory, Graduate School of Civil, Environmental and Urban Engineering, University of Lyon, CNRS, Vaulx-en-Velin, France), and Joana Ralão (Contemporary History at the Faculty of Social Sciences and Humanities of NOVA University Lisbon, Portugal).

This document was developed under the guidance of the working group, invited participants and guest advisors, through a process of co-creation. Efforts were made to engage a broad range of members, both through a structured survey and a series of informal consultations with individuals who expressed interest in contributing. Based on the analysis of the information collected, a series of draft documents was shared, and new documents were developed, with the final draft of documents shared at the workshop. The advantages and limitations of this process were recognised from the outset. Although it is a transparent process that allows all participants to contribute their views, on the other hand, time constraints, unforeseen circumstances, and other practical challenges have emerged as its main limitations.

Acknowledgements

We would like to express our sincere gratitude to everyone who took the time to respond to the questionnaire, as well as to all participants in the co-creation meeting. Your valuable contributions and active engagement were greatly appreciated and played an important role in supporting our work.

Vision

SHiFT CA21166 Action aims to leverage Social Sciences, Humanities, and Arts (SSH&A) to address societal transformations necessary for climate resilience. Consistent with its MoU, SHiFT promotes inclusive participation, interdisciplinary collaboration, and evidence-based approaches to social and environmental challenges. Aligned with Sustainable Development Goals, SHiFT emphasises:

1. **Gender Equality (Goal 5)** – Empower and ensure equal opportunities, leadership, representation, and participation for all genders within SHiFT programs and initiatives.
2. **Sustainable Development (Goals 7, 12, 13, 15)** – Incorporating environmentally responsible practices, promoting resource efficiency, and supporting initiatives that combat climate change and preserve biodiversity.
3. **Inclusive Growth (Goal 8)** – Encouraging equitable access to economic opportunities, skills development, and fair treatment for all employees and participants.
4. **Partnerships for the Goals (Goal 17)** – Collaborating with stakeholders to foster gender-inclusive and sustainable solutions that align with OECD recommendations.

To create gender-sensitive, inclusive, and equitable research, fostering leadership, participation, and decision-making opportunities for all genders, following COTS and one of the European Union’s main goals: to promote gender equality in research and innovation (EUROPEAN COMMISSION, 2020).

SHiFT COST Action is fully committed to promoting diversity and inclusion across all its activities. Equal opportunities for participation will be ensured for women and men, as well as for early-career and senior researchers, and for participants from all countries, with special attention to the Inclusiveness Target Countries (ITCs).

1. Introduction

In the scope of the European Cooperation in Science and Technology (COST), the SHiFT Gender Equality and Inclusion Plan (SGEIP) aim to improve SHiFT's commitment to fairness, transparency, and equal opportunity. By creating a culture that is sensitive to gender, promoting talented women and men in research and innovation, making sure there is a mix of people from different places, and making sure that people are at different stages in their careers, SHiFT enhances the quality of its outputs and contributes to broader societal transformation.

In the context where fundamental ethical values are being questioned, it is crucial to engage in in-depth discussion and critical reflection. It is also important that the entire process of developing the tools is as transparent and inclusive as possible. SHiFT has a key role in promoting equal opportunities and gender-sensitive practices across all activities.

SHiFT in numbers^{1*}:

- Shift COST Action has an average of 62% women's representation
- 60% researchers' positions are held by women
- 43% of Action Chairs and 56% of Action Vice-Chairs are women
- 65% of the total young participants in COST Actions are women
- 67% of ITC participants in COST Actions are women

According to the SHiFT MoU, to produce high-quality research, work fairly together, and achieve sustainable impact, gender equality and inclusion are essential. This plan aims to identify barriers, define priorities, and promote equal opportunities for all members of our community.

¹ Note: * These numbers are from 2024. In September 2024, the COST Action SHiFT had 382 registered members. From [COST CA21166](https://www.cost.eu/actions/CA21166/) webpage members:

<https://www.cost.eu/actions/CA21166/>

The current list of Inclusiveness Target Countries (ITCs) include: Albania, Armenia, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Cyprus, Czech Republic, Estonia, Croatia, Georgia, Greece, Hungary, Lithuania, Latvia, Malta, Moldova, Montenegro, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovenia, Slovakia, Republic of North Macedonia, Republic of Serbia, Türkiye and Ukraine. The ITCs are defined at: <https://www.cost.eu/about/strategy/excellence-and-inclusiveness/>

2. Objectives

Three strategic objectives serve as motivation for the development of this SGEIP: 1) to contribute to the effective integration of positive gender equality and inclusion in SHiFT's activities and outputs. All individuals, including gender, age, career stage, or country of origin, are to be ensured equal access, respect, and opportunities within this COST Action. 2) to involve and develop a framework that fosters a common understanding of gender equality and inclusion among SHiFT members. 3) to create practical tools to be applied in practice that help to reshape gender equality, inclusion and diversity respect, not only in activities but also in their outputs and tools to be deployed within the framework of their activities.

To achieve these objectives, the SGEIP was developed through a co-creation process grounded in a shared perspective, guided by a set of principles and practical tools. This collaborative initiative was built in five objectives: a) To foster a gender-sensitive and inclusive environment across all SHiFT WG and activities; b) To promote gender equality in participation, leadership, and decision-making; c) To provide support and the resources to reduce barriers for underrepresented individuals; d) To conduct a review of the relevant legal and policy frameworks; e) To empower researchers and practitioners (innovators, teachers, policy-makers, educators, among others) across different disciplines and geographical locations to critically reflect on their work, challenge biases and design inclusive interventions while granting gender equality.

A dedicated working group was set up and developed in a co-creation process to involve as many participating members as possible and promote debate. With this informal group, various tools were developed, building on the findings of the first survey report to address the most pressing needs. An Open Letter was drafted, the SHiFT Plan for Gender Equality and Inclusion was discussed, a webpage was created, and a new survey was developed. This enabled the framework and foundations for integrating the SGEIP principles to be updated and adapted. By developing these tools, the initiative aims to raise awareness, monitor progress and support the implementation of gender strategies.

3. Principles

The SHiFT Gender Equality and Inclusion Plan is based on five principles: Equity, Diversity, Transparency, Participation, and Accountability. These principles shape our commitment to building a fair and inclusive research and innovation environment within the Action.

- **Equity** has been fostered by creating a gender-sensitive and inclusive environment across all SHiFT Working Groups and activities, ensuring that members are supported to engage on equal terms.
- **Diversity** has been promoted through active measures to strengthen gender equality in participation, leadership, and decision-making, while also encouraging contributions from individuals representing a wide range of disciplines, cultural contexts, and career stages.
- **Transparency** underpins the way SHiFT designs and implements its activities. By making processes clear and accessible, we have sought to reduce barriers and provide the necessary resources for underrepresented individuals to thrive.
- **Participation** is at the heart of SHiFT. Researchers and practitioners, including innovators, teachers, policy-makers, and educators, are empowered to critically reflect on their work, challenge biases, and design inclusive interventions that advance gender equality.
- Finally, **accountability** ensures that commitments to gender equality and inclusion are translated into practice. Progress is monitored and reported, holding SHiFT collectively responsible for creating an environment where every member has the opportunity to contribute fully and meaningfully.

The SGEIP was not a standalone initiative, but a dynamic and adaptive strategy designed to foster inclusiveness, respect, and gender equality. Its ultimate aim was to ensure that gender considerations were embedded at every stage of SHiFT's work. A structured participation plan has been designed to promote gender equality and embed diversity, respect, and inclusive practices within the SHiFT network. This plan ensures that different people are involved in the actions and has a lasting impact by encouraging people to share what they know and learn together.

4. Key Actions

4.1. Survey Implementation

- Collect data on the current perceptions and experiences within the they're on Institution and SHiFT action.
- Understand their view of the main problems.
- Investigate possible solutions.
- Check which members of SHiFT and beyond want to be part of the working group to design the tools and write a future article.

4.2. Working Group & Invited Advisors

Set up a dedicated SHiFT Gender Equality and Inclusion Working Group. This group ensures that different people are involved in the actions and has a lasting impact by encouraging people to share what they know and learn together.

Three Guest Advisors: 1) One Early Career Researcher (ECR) Representative will ensure that the perspectives of young researchers are fully represented. This will contribute to the design of the workshop and career development resources and will support outreach to engage more women and non-binary individuals in SHiFT activities. 2) An independent expert will be invited to provide regular assessments of the SGEIP, offering critical feedback and strategic guidance based on best practices in gender equality in research and innovation. 3) One senior member representative of the SHiFT network from diverse disciplinary backgrounds will serve as a mentor to Young Researchers and Innovators.

4.2. Training and Capacity Building

- Organize webinars, workshops, and seminars on gender equality and inclusiveness.
- Provide practical sources with guidelines for integrating gender considerations into research design, data collection, and dissemination.

4.3. Policy and Procedures

- Develop a **Gender Equality and Inclusiveness Open Letter** to be adopted by SHiFT COST Action.
- Incorporate gender criteria in grant applications, progress reports, and deliverables.
- Ensure gender-balanced composition of Steering Committees and Working Groups.

4.4. Monitoring and Evaluation

- Collect gender-disaggregated data on participation, leadership, and outputs.
- Conduct annual **surveys** and evaluations to assess progress and identify areas for improvement.
- Report findings in public documents to enhance transparency.

4.5. Awareness and Communication

- Publish an **Open Letter** promoting gender equality principles.
- Disseminate best practices, case studies, and success stories across COST networks through the **Webpage**.
- Celebrate: Women's day in science, 11 February or International Women's Day, 8 March.

5. Outcomes

The general outcomes are:

- Increased gender balance in participation and leadership across SHiFT' COST Action (CA21166).
- Improved awareness and integration of gender considerations in research processes.
- A sustainable culture of inclusivity and ethical responsibility.

- Measurable progress towards equal opportunities and gender-friendly career advancement.

5.1. SURVEY SGEIP

5.1.1. Survey Tool - SHiFT Gender Equality and Inclusion Plan

As part of the development of the SHiFT Gender Equality and Inclusion Plan, a survey was designed to gain a deeper understanding of the perspectives, experiences, and needs of the SHiFT community in relation to gender balance, diversity, and inclusion. The aim of this survey was to provide evidence-based insights that could guide the identification of priorities and the formulation of targeted actions within the plan.

We use a wide range of references, of which we highlight the International Science Council. (2025)², UNESCO (2019)³, United Nations Population Fund (2022)⁴, GIA⁵; RESET co-designed a Gender Equality survey⁶, GEAM tool (2019)⁷ and GESI framework (2018)⁸, which provides a comprehensive approach to integrate gender and social inclusion principles across activities and policies.

² International Science Council. (2025). *Survey: Gender equality in scientific organizations*. <https://council.science/news/2025-gender-equality-in-scientific-organizations-survey/>

³ UNESCO. (2019). Gender equality in education: Looking beyond parity. <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000266145>

⁴ UNFPA & Equimundo. (2022, June). *International Men & Gender Equality Survey (IMAGES)*. Retrieved from <https://www.unfpa.org/publications/international-men-gender-equality-survey-images>

⁵ RESET Project. (n.d.). *GIA Checklist*. <https://wereset.eu/gia-checklist/>

⁶ RESET Project. (n.d.). Gender Equality Survey [Survey]. RESET. <https://wereset.eu/gender-equality-survey/>

⁷ ACT Project. (2019). Gender Equality Audit and Monitoring (GEAM) Tool [Tool]. Advance HE; Notus; Open University of Catalonia. <https://geam.act-on-gender.eu>

⁸ DFID, SDC, & Irish Aid. (2018). *A Common Framework for Gender Equality & Social Inclusion (GESI Framework)*. <https://asiapacific.unwomen.org/en/digital-library/publications/2017/04/gesi-framework>

5.1.2. Methodology

In line with established methodological guidelines for social research, a structured, closed-ended questionnaire was developed. The survey was designed to take no longer than five minutes to complete, thereby encouraging higher participation rates and minimising respondent fatigue.

The questionnaire was organised into five distinct sections, each addressing a specific area of inquiry.

- The first section, Demographics, collected basic information such as gender, age group, country of residence, and professional background, in order to contextualise responses.
- The second section, Institution, Research and Activities, sought to gather data regarding the respondent's institutional affiliation, level of involvement, and the extent to which gender considerations are embedded within their organisation's structure and research practices.
- The third section, similar to the one before but focused on gender topics within the SHiFT COST Action, assesses participants' understanding, engagement, and perspectives on gender-related themes specifically within the SHiFT network.
- The fourth section aimed to invite respondents to participate in ongoing or forthcoming SHiFT activities related to gender equality and inclusion, aligning with the overall objectives of the COST Action.
- Finally, the fifth section explored whether respondents' professional activities were already connected to gender-related issues, thereby providing insight into prior experience and expertise within the field.

The survey is provided in the annexe and is available at the following link: https://docs.google.com/forms/d/1_GPI5q651wJeFVg2xZTyR5i8odV36o5PJSxwbzz6oPo/edit

5.2. Survey A.1. Method, Results & Discussion

5.2.1. Method

The first survey, conducted in August and September 2025, sought input from members of the Action across various backgrounds, career stages, and countries. By capturing a diverse range of “voices”, the process was intended to ensure that the plan reflects the collective experience of the network and is grounded in the realities faced by its members.

All responses were anonymised and securely stored in accordance with data protection regulations. Quantitative data were analysed using descriptive statistics to summarise frequencies, percentages, and trends across the five sections of the survey. Where relevant, cross-tabulations were performed to explore relationships between respondent characteristics (such as professional background or institutional role) and engagement with gender-related issues. SPSS was used for the more complex analyses.

By the end of September 2025, a total of 56 valid responses had been collected. This represented a significant contribution from the SHiFT members, providing a valuable foundation for drawing SGEIP commitments.

The sample was estimated based on **Krejcie and Morgan’s recommendations** (Almeida & Freire, 2007), which state that for a population of 5,000 individuals and a margin of error below 5%, a representative sample should include at least 350 participants. Within this framework, the number of responses obtained can be considered adequate to provide a reliable indication of the perspectives within the Action, thereby ensuring the validity of the subsequent analyses.

5.2.2. Results

A total of **56 individuals** completed the survey, drawn from a target population of **382 members** of the COST Action SHiFT network, corresponding to **14.7%** of the population.

Demographics

Table 1 How do participants in your COST Action describe themselves?

	Participation	Leadership positions	Young participants	ITC participants
Women	77%	83%	71%	67%
Men	23%	17%	29%	33%
Non-binary	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0
Prefer not to say	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0
Do not identify as woman, man, or non-binary. Please specify how you would identify	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0

The results of the SHiFT survey on gender equity and inclusion show that, of the 56 valid responses collected, the majority came from women, who accounted for 77% of respondents (Fig. 1). Within this group, 46% identified as participants, 7% reported holding leadership positions, and 4% were ITC participants.

Figure 1: Distribution of survey responses regarding gender balance within SHiFT.

The majority of respondents are at the senior career stage, with senior researchers representing 42% of all participants, reflecting strong engagement among experienced members of SHiFT (Fig 3). Young participants presented the most balanced representation in the survey, contributing 5% of the total responses (Table 1). In terms of age distribution, respondents were relatively well spread across different career stages: 32% were aged 50–59 years, 32% were 40–49 years, 23% were 30–39 years, and 7% were under 30. This indicates that participation is not limited to a single age or career stage but includes members from a broad professional spectrum (Fig 2).

Figure 2: Distribution of survey responses regarding age balance within SHiFT.

Overall, the findings highlight both strengths and challenges for SHiFT. The high level of female representation indicates that women are strongly engaged in the network’s activities.

Figure 3: Distribution of survey responses regarding position balance within SHiFT.

Institutional and Research contexts

Figure 4: Does your institution, research group, or company have a Gender Equality Plan or similar?

Notably, half of SHiFT members (52%) reported that their home institution has a Gender Plan or a similar framework in place, highlighting a positive baseline of institutional support for gender equality across the network (Fig. 4). However, 18% of participants indicated that they were unsure or did not know whether such a framework exists.

Gender Topics within the Scientific Environment vs SHiFT COST Action

Figure 5: Have you ever witnessed or heard of someone experiencing gender-based discrimination? (Left) In a scientific environment 29% contrasting with (Right) within the COST Action SHiFT environment 88%

However, when asked whether they have ever witnessed or experienced gender-based discrimination in their home institution or within the COST Action SHiFT environment, the survey revealed a clear contrast. Within their home institutions, 59% of respondents reported having seen or heard about instances of gender-based discrimination (Fig 6). In contrast, in the SHiFT environment, the majority of responses were negative, with 88% indicating that they had not observed or experienced such discrimination. These findings emphasise the need to complement institutional policies with active monitoring, awareness-raising, and inclusive practices, while also highlighting that SHiFT has been successful in creating a relatively safe and equitable environment for its members.

When respondents were asked, “*What do you see as the main barriers to achieving gender equality?*”, the survey revealed a complex landscape of challenges within the SHiFT community (Fig. 6). Structural and institutional obstacles emerged as the most prominent barrier, reported by 61% of participants, highlighting the enduring influence of organisational frameworks on gender parity. Implicit biases were also widely recognised, with 57% of respondents acknowledging their impact, while 54% identified difficulties in balancing family and work responsibilities as a significant constraint. Furthermore, 45% of participants pointed to a general lack of awareness, underscoring the need for continued education and dialogue on gender issues.

These findings illustrate that barriers to gender equality are multifaceted, spanning both systemic structures and cultural attitudes. They point to the necessity of implementing targeted strategies, including awareness-raising initiatives, bias mitigation measures, and institutional policies that actively support work–life balance, to cultivate an environment that is truly equitable and inclusive.

Figure 6: “*What do you see as the main barriers to achieving gender equality?*”

Measures & Strategies

When asked, “*What sort of support or actions would improve gender equality?*”, respondents identified several complementary measures. First action, with 61%, was gender equality monitoring. Second, with a half of the respondents (50%), gender-sensitive communication and careful planning of events; followed by 48% of responses

with recommended awareness training on gender bias as a critical step. Mentorship programmes for underrepresented genders were also considered valuable, with 39% of participants identifying them to support career progression and foster equal opportunities.

Participation in SHiFT activities related to gender equality and inclusion

When respondents were asked about their willingness to participate in ongoing or forthcoming SHiFT activities related to gender equality and inclusion, most expressed interest in being involved. This question aimed to assess the level of engagement and motivation among participants to contribute actively to the implementation of the COST Action’s objectives. The responses provided valuable insight into the potential for collaboration, capacity-building, and future involvement within the SHiFT network.

Table 2: Willingness to participate in ongoing or forthcoming SHiFT activities related to gender equality and inclusion

In the near future, would you like to actively participate:	% (n)
As a participant in the webinar?	68% (38)
As a presenter on the webinar?	38% (21)
In the working group to prepare the webinar?	50% (28)
In the gender equality Open Letter?	50% (28)
As a representative of early-career researchers of SGEIP?	16% (9)
As an independent expert of SGEIP?	29% (16)
As a senior member representative of SGEIP?	30% (17)
In a SGEIP article?	52% (29)

In this question, respondents were also invited to provide their email addresses for potential future contact regarding SHiFT activities and follow-up initiatives (Table 2).

This allowed the identification of individuals interested in maintaining engagement and contributing to forthcoming actions within the network.

Integration of Gender Perspectives in Professional Practice

The majority of respondents who answered the questions *“Have you taken gender considerations into account: in recruitment processes, job assignments, or career development opportunities; in the composition of the project coordination or conference team; or in the process of collecting a new sample for your research?”* reported that they were already engaged with gender-related issues or expressed a clear interest in this area (Table 3). This indicates that many participants possess prior experience or a proactive attitude towards integrating gender considerations within their professional practice, highlighting both existing expertise and the potential for further involvement in gender-focused initiatives.

Table 3: Integration of Gender Perspectives in Professional Practice

Have you taken gender considerations into account?	No	Yes	Partially	Not applicable
In recruitment processes, job assignments, or career development opportunities?	13%	59%	13%	16%
In the composition of the project coordination team or the conference team?	16%	54%	18%	13%
In the process of collecting a new sample for your research?	9%	64%	11%	16%

5.2.3. Survey A.1. Discussion & Recommendations

As part of the development of the SHiFT Gender Equality and Inclusion Plan, a survey was conducted to gain a deeper understanding of the perspectives, experiences, and needs of the SHiFT community regarding gender balance, diversity, and inclusion.

The survey aimed to provide evidence-based insights to guide the identification of priorities and the formulation of targeted actions within the Plan. Drawing on established

frameworks and references, including the International Science Council (2025), UNESCO (2019), the United Nations Population Fund (2022), as well as tools such as the GEAM survey (RESET, 2019) and the GESI Framework (2018), the survey was designed to capture both structural and cultural dimensions of gender and social inclusion within the network.

Although the findings are not fully representative, they offer an overview of current engagement, institutional support, and individual experiences related to gender equality within SHiFT members.

The overall results suggest that promoting gender equality within SHiFT requires a mix of structural measures, awareness-raising, and targeted support. By combining these approaches, the network can enhance inclusion, ensure fair participation, and create a professional environment where all members are able to contribute fully.

- **Main barriers identified:** Structural/institutional obstacles (61%), implicit biases (57%), family/work balance (54%), and lack of awareness (45%) were identified as the key challenges to achieving gender equality within SHiFT.
- **Supportive actions identified:** The following methods were found to be effective ways to improve inclusion: Regular gender equality monitoring (61%), Gender-sensitive communication and event planning (50%), Awareness training on gender bias (48%), and Mentorship programmes for underrepresented genders (39%).
- **Key insight:** The participants consider that the barriers to equality and inclusion, in general, are both systemic and cultural, requiring a combination of monitoring, awareness-raising, and targeted/training support initiatives.
- **Implication:** Implementing these actions will foster a more inclusive, equitable, and supportive environment, enabling all members to participate and contribute fully.

The survey findings therefore provide not only a snapshot of the current situation but also a valuable evidence base to guide future actions and policies under the Gender Equality and Inclusion Plan. In this regard, it is imperative that this cost action seeks greater participation from men in the future.

The SHiFT Gender Equality and Inclusion survey provides some valuable insights into the perspectives, experiences, and engagement of members regarding gender balance, diversity, and inclusion. However, most participants in the survey were already connected with these issues. It is essential to publicise the upcoming survey and encourage new participants, particularly men, to join the COST action SHiFT.

5.3. SHiFT Gender Equality & Inclusion Working Group & Advisors:

All SHiFT Cost Action members were invited to take part of the working group. The Working Group was created to foster deeper discussion in the development of the various instruments and to increase awareness and dissemination of the Gender Equality and Inclusion Plan.

In response to the underrepresentation of men in both the survey responses and the composition of the Working Group, direct invitations were extended to full members of the COST Action and to other potentially interested stakeholders.

Several meetings were held, each contributing to the design and refinement of the instruments and new ideas flourished. It was often difficult to get everyone together at the same time, but the plan was always to make sure that all members could share their ideas and speak their mind.

The participants were kind and worked well together. They have been very important in creating a plan for SHiFT that is more open and meaningful.

Joana Ralão

Early Career Researcher (ECR) Expert will ensure that the perspectives of young researchers are fully represented. She will support outreach to engage more women and non-binary individuals in SHiFT activities.

Isabel Cunha

An independent expert will be invited to provide regular assessments of the SGEIP, offering critical feedback and strategic guidance based on best practices in gender equality in research and innovation.

Besa Shahini

Senior Expert in the SHiFT Gender Equality and Inclusivity network survey. As Senior Advisor, offering critical feedback and strategic guidance to mentor the group and share your opinions on the instruments we are developing.

Figure 7: Guest Advisors of SHiFT Gender Equality & Inclusion

Three advisers were invited (Figure 7):

- Besa Shahine - Senior member of the SHiFT network and advisor from diverse disciplinary backgrounds, serving as a mentor to Young Researchers and Innovators, while encouraging mentorship programs that support the participation of underrepresented genders in leadership roles.
- Isabel Cunha - Independent expert, responsible for providing regular assessments of the SGEIP, offering critical feedback and strategic guidance based on best practices in gender equality in research and innovation.
- Joana Ralão - Early Career Researcher (ECR) Representative, ensuring that the perspectives of young researchers are fully integrated.

5.4. Survey A.2. & A.3. Tools

5.4.1. Survey A.2.

Undertaken with the collective support of all, and under the leadership of Besa Shahini. Following the first survey, the questionnaire was further refined and discussed in a large group setting, resulting in a revised version to be implemented between

October and December 2025. A report presenting the results of this second round will be included at a later stage. The improved Tool and the outcome of the template, led by our senior advisor Besa Shahine, is available as an annexe and serves as a working tool.

The final survey is provided in the annexe and is available at the following link:
https://docs.google.com/forms/d/13ld4q6TM8swDcsdLL6N-e5-SF_XfqMJxUwYoqhVrLUs/edit

The working document is provided at the following link:
https://docs.google.com/document/d/1_Uc5Qj2vTqBoCb-w4LguJdrWy0YRkAcnW8jtCEVNAnk/edit?usp=sharing

5.4.2. Survey for activities

A survey framework was designed to allow adaptation for post-activity evaluation. Following the discussion initiated by the Open Letter, a new tool was created to further support the implementation and monitoring of activities.

Survey-based activities (<https://forms.gle/KVjd3oHpk4NhhSL36>)

5.5. Open Letter (Tool)

The open letter expresses political and institutional support for the SHiFT network's activities, recognising the importance of embedding gender equality and inclusion-sensitive approaches across all levels of the Action.

The SHiFT COST Action is committed to implementing concrete policies to promote diversity, equity, and inclusion across all its activities. Equal opportunities will be guaranteed for women and men, early-career and senior researchers, and participants from all countries, with particular attention to Inclusiveness Target Countries (ITCs). These policies are grounded in the founding principles of this COST Action and are based on a vision of open, inclusive and innovative scientific cooperation. The SHiFT CA21166 Action is guided by five core principles: Equity, Diversity, Transparency, Participation, and Accountability, which collectively shape a fair, inclusive, and sustainable research environment.

SHiFT promotes the exchange of transdisciplinary knowledge to drive social transformations in the face of climate change. This document is a product of open collaboration, knowledge-sharing and the exchange of best practices.

Policy Measures to be Applied:

5.5.1. Equity and Non-discrimination

Ensuring that, in all SHiFT activities, there is equal access, respect and opportunities regardless of gender, age, career stage or country of origin, with special attention to the Target Countries for Inclusion, within the scope of this COST Action.

5.5.2. Diversity and Inclusion

Every SHiFT program, activity or conference should include a paragraph clearly stating the commitment to diversity, inclusion and gender equality. This will ensure that every event, funding opportunity or collaborative activity promotes participation regardless of gender, age, career stage or country of origin. Specific actions can still focus on particular groups to ensure their inclusion.

5.5.3. Transparency

Each SHiFT program/activity report must include a paragraph explaining how the program/activity has championed diversity, inclusion and gender equality, both in its design and in the composition of participants. This paragraph should document both the absence of discrimination and the proactive measures taken to ensure equal participation regardless of gender, age, career stage or country of origin.

5.5.4. Participation and Gender-Sensitive Practices

Researchers, practitioners, educators, and policymakers are empowered to actively participate.

- Ensure a gender-sensitive language is used in all calls, documents, and announcements.
- The host of training schools and workshops will pay attention to equal representation of trainers and participants.

- The online meetings will be scheduled at family-friendly times (avoid late evenings/weekends).
- Include sessions on unconscious bias, inclusive research practices, and gender-sensitive innovation. In addition, case studies that highlight how inclusiveness enhances research quality and innovation will be promoted.
- Provide hybrid/online participation options to support caregivers, parents, and those with mobility constraints. Ensure physical and digital accessibility for all events.

5.5.5. Accountability and Monitoring

Commitments to gender equality and inclusion are actively monitored and reported.

- Include a survey at the end of each activity. This survey will not only gather feedback for future improvements but also monitor and ensure quality control and transparency.
- At the end of each activity or funding allocation, a summary report of the applications and recipients should be available, ensuring transparency and allowing the community to review the distribution and impact of the resources.

These policies/ common protocols aim to foster an inclusive, equitable, and collaborative environment, strengthen intergenerational and cross-sectoral cooperation, and ensure that SHiFT's activities generate both scientific excellence and societal benefit.

This open letter was improved through several contributions, resulting in this version.

5.6. WEB-Page SEIP

Undertaken with the collective support of all, and under the leadership of Joana Ralão.

5.6.1. Objectives

- Foster discussion and debate to achieve the effective integration of positive gender equality and inclusion in SHiFT's activities and outputs.
- Promote and highlight SHiFT diversity, including gender, age, career stage, scientific areas or country of origin.
- Provide direct access to relevant platforms and resources, enabling all participants can fully engage and contribute to the COST Action's objectives.
- Also provide links to training platforms, toolkits, and networks supporting inclusiveness.
- Inclusive language and communication

5.6.2. Support information to be included

Gender Equality & Inclusion

“Fostering equity, diversity and inclusion in SHiFT”

The SHiFT Gender Equality and Inclusive Plan (SGEIP) aims to improve SHiFT's commitment to fairness, transparency, and equal opportunity. By cultivating a gender-sensitive culture, SHiFT enhances the quality of its outputs and contributes to broader societal transformation.

Women's rights and gender equality face growing challenges in various societies, including COST Member Countries and others participating in COST Actions. In this context, fundamental ethical values are being questioned, making it crucial to engage in thorough discussion and critical reflection. It is possible that, without conscious awareness, we may inadvertently act in ways that are not fully fair. COST has a key role in promoting equal opportunities and gender-sensitive practices across all activities.

To learn more about this initiative, please click on the documents below:

- SHiFT Gender Equality and Inclusion Plan
- Survey
- Open Letter

This is a collective endeavour. Together, we can make SHiFT a stronger, more inclusive and equitable community. Got ideas to share? Your voice matters! Please send us your thoughts: cost.shift.sgeip@gmail.com

5.6.3. Canvas design

Figure 8: Canvas design proposal for webpage

To access to web design - [Design canva](#)

5.7. Co-Creation Meeting/Webinar

The SHiFT COST Action is fully aligned with COST’s commitment to promoting gender equality and to supporting talented women and men in research and innovation, as outlined in the COST Excellence and Inclusiveness Policy.

In this context, an online Co-Creation Meeting/webinar was held on 30 September 2025 by the working group, in collaboration with advisors, to discuss gender-sensitive

research and present the various instruments developed by the group. The aim was to promote discussion, raise awareness, and build skills, knowledge, and competencies related to gender equality and mainstreaming strategies. This Online Co-Creation Meeting: Gender Equality and Inclusion supported interdisciplinary dialogue and participatory tool refinement, contributing to the MoU's objective of enhancing knowledge exchange and providing space for collaborative innovation in policy and practice.

All members were invited to participate, and the working instruments were made available in advance. The webinar was also published on the SHiFT website (<https://shift-cost.eu/online-co-creation-meeting-gender-equality-and-inclusive/>). As the instruments are interactive, they continued to receive valuable feedback, including from members who were unable to attend the meeting. In this regard, the event was considered highly successful.

The session further served to consolidate key messages, best practices, and calls to Action emerging from the results and broader consultations. The meeting was intended to serve as a dissemination and advocacy tool, amplifying SHiFT's collective "voice" in wider conversations on gender and climate research. The instruments will remain open for ongoing discussion, refinement and improvement.

The flyer is provided in annexe and at the following link:
(https://drive.google.com/file/d/1rz-LEENrbr-cy_9L4dgmXoPcknytlCbd/view)

6. Implementation Future Action

The outcomes informed evidence-based future strategies, helping SHiFT and its partners implement targeted interventions, monitor progress, and ensure that gender equality is systematically considered in all aspects of the Action. Ultimately, such support strengthens the capacity of SHiFT to create an inclusive, diverse, and fair research environment. Our goal was to empower all members to contribute fully to the network's scientific and societal goals.

The survey report provided a fact-based assessment of how gender inclusiveness can be implemented in SHiFT's COST Action. The results helped identify the main gaps

and informed future interventions, directly supporting the research coordination objectives of the SGEIP by aligning SHiFT's gender strategies with empirical insights.

The Workshop for co-creation brought together action members to discuss gender-sensitive research and presented the findings of the A.1. report. It aimed to support interdisciplinary dialogue and participatory tool refinement. It contributed to the MoU's objective of enhancing knowledge exchange and provided space for collaborative innovation in policy and practice.

In summary, future action objectives:

- **Action participation and leadership** – Encourage balanced representation in leadership roles and participation from underrepresented groups.
- **Meeting and event hosting and participation** – Rotate locations, support remote access, and provide funding for participants from diverse backgrounds.
- **Fostering research collaborations** – Promote partnerships across countries, disciplines, and career stages.
- **Grant calls** – Design calls that are accessible, fair, and inclusive, with clear criteria to support diversity.
- **Training school** – Offers affordable, widely accessible training with travel grants for those from underrepresented regions.
- **Communications strategies/ Webinars** – Use inclusive language, accessible formats, and multiple channels to reach a wide audience.
- **Early-career researchers' development** – Provide mentorship, networking opportunities, and targeted support for early-career researchers.

6.1. Operational Tools for Gender & Inclusive Action

6.1.1. Survey A.2. and Survey A.2. Report

It will assess how gender inclusivity is perceived and operationalised in SHiFT activities, namely in training and collaborative events. This tool contributes to research coordination and capacity building by establishing a replicable method of monitoring gender equity across disciplines and project phases. In its development, it took into

account national and European ethics and research integrity rules (such as the **EU Ethics in Social Sciences and Humanities** and the **European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity**), which usually consider sex and gender identity as **Special Categories of Personal Data**.

6.1.2. Survey-based activities

A survey framework was designed to allow adaptation for post-activity evaluation.

(<https://forms.gle/KVjd3oHpk4NhhSL36>)

6.1.3. Workshop/Webinar

To consolidate key messages, best practices, and calls to action emerging from the results and broader consultations. Promote and discuss the Open Letter is intended to serve as both a dissemination and advocacy tool, amplifying SHiFT's "voices" in wider conversations on gender and climate research and helping to influence institutional policies beyond the Action itself. It should remain under discussion and improvement.

The SHiFT Gender Equality and Inclusive Plan (SGEIP) supports and reinforces the specific objectives of the SHiFT Memorandum of Understanding. By making sure that gender equality and inclusiveness are a part of all of SHiFT's activities, SGEIP makes sure that research coordination and efforts to build capacity are fair, diverse, and respond to society. It contributes to the hybridization and triangulation of ideas by introducing critical gender perspectives into transdisciplinary collaboration. The development of inclusive guidelines and training strengthens co-creation practices and encourages innovation rooted in equity. This objective underpinned the design of the new workshops.

Two additional workshops/webinars are planned for development. Training activity with the invited expert Isabel Cunha, 12 February 2026 (to be approved). General meeting 8 March to exchange knowledge and to promote gender balance and inclusive representation, it is our intention to also invite a male expert to join the COST Action as a special guest and gather training and capacity building dimensions (to be approved).

6.1.4. Webpage

To support transparency and support equal access, a dedicated webpage is developed to house all materials. Including SGEIP methodology, Survey A.2., and the Open Letter. Monthly.

6.1.5. Article

The SGEI Working Group will develop a scientific article based on the findings of the A1 and A2 surveys, as well as the outcomes of the workshop. This article will form part of SHiFT's broader dissemination strategy and will include the final version of the Open Letter, helping to consolidate and communicate SHiFT's commitment to gender equality and inclusive research across Europe.

6.2. Roadmap for Future Action

Table 2: Roadmap for Future Action 2026

Phase	Actions	Responsible	Timeline 2026
Phase 1	Improve SGEIP, existing tools and methodological skills	Action advisors & working group	Months 1–2
Phase 2	Organise training & webinars to promote gender-inclusive practices. Workshop –guest expert invited.	WG members & advisors	Months 2–4
Phase 3	Launch Open Letter & Awareness Campaign	Communication team	Months 3–5
Phase 4	Monitoring & Evaluation Progress: Conduct Survey A.2 Prepare Survey A.2 Report	Evaluation team	Months 4-8 Months 9-10
Phase 5	scientific article	SGEIP working group	Months 1-7

Notes:

- The outcomes of these phases aim to inform future evidence-based strategies. Also, support targeted interventions and ensure systematic consideration of gender equality across all SHiFT activities.

- Activities are designed to strengthen inclusive participation, interdisciplinary collaboration, and capacity building among members.
- All tools and outputs (Survey A.2 & A.3., Open Letter, Webpage) contribute to transparency, dissemination, and sustainable knowledge exchange.

6.3. Final notes.

Summarily, a framework was developed to support the development of a shared understanding. The above plan demonstrates our commitment to diversity and inclusivity. It goes far beyond merely participating in the Action to holistically integrate, foster and enhance diversity in terms of age, geography and gender in all aspects of Action activities. We firmly believe that this approach will yield long-term benefits, extending well beyond the lifetime of the Action.

The SHiFT Gender Equality and Inclusive Plan seeks to advance SHiFT's ambition to establish a transdisciplinary Hub capable of driving timely societal transformations in the context of climate change. As SHiFT brings together researchers and practitioners from diverse social sciences and humanities backgrounds, to exchange knowledge, learn new techniques, and working across political, economic, environmental, and technological spheres, integrating gender equality and inclusiveness is essential for ensuring that the resulting transformations are just, representative, and effective.

This document is not intended to be viewed as a finalised work, but rather as the initial stage of a continuing process of refinement and collaboration.

7. References

7.1. SGEIP References

All European Academies (ALLEA). (2017). *The European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity* (Revised Edition). ALLEA. https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/guidance/european-code-of-conduct-for-researchintegrity_horizon_en.pdf

Almeida, L. S., & Freire, T. (2008). *Metodologia da Investigação em Psicologia e Educação* (5.^a ed.). Psiquilíbrios.

COST Association. (2024). *Gender Equality Plan for COST Actions* (v2.7.0.2). <https://www.cost.eu/uploads/2024/11/GEP-template-for-COST-Actions-v27022025.pdf>

COST Association. (2024). *Gender Equality Plan for COST Activities*. <https://www.cost.eu/uploads/2024/11/COST-Gender-Equality-Plan-07112024.pdf>

COST Association. (n.d.). *Gender equality*. <https://www.cost.eu/about/strategy/gender-equality/>

DFID, SDC, & Irish Aid. (2018). A Common Framework for Gender Equality & Social Inclusion (GESI Framework). <https://asiapacific.unwomen.org/en/digital-library/publications/2017/04/gesi-framework>

Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, European Commission. (2021). *Ethics in Social Sciences and Humanities*. https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/guidance/ethics-in-social-science-andhumanities_he_en.pdf

Equimundo. (2022). *The International Men & Gender Equality Survey: A Status Report in 15 Headlines*. https://www.unfpa.org/sites/default/files/pub-pdf/International%20Men%20%26%20Gender%20Equality%20Survey%20%28IMAGES%29%20Global%20Report%202022_EN.pdf

European Commission. (2020). *Gender equality in research and innovation*. Retrieved October 2, 2025, from https://ec.europa.eu/info/gender-equality-research_en

European Commission. (2020). *Gender equality strategy 2020-2025*. <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/33fc19b1-74a5-11ef-a8ba-01aa75ed71a1/language-en>

European Commission. (n.d.). *Gender equality in research and innovation*. https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/strategy-research-and-innovation/democracy-and-rights/gender-equality-research-and-innovation_en

European Institute for Gender Equality. (2022). *Gender equality plans in academia and research: Roadmap to effective implementation*. https://eige.europa.eu/sites/default/files/documents/roadmap_to_effective_implementation_of_gps.pdf

International Development Partners Group Nepal. (2017). *A common framework for gender equality & social inclusion*. UN Women. <https://asiapacific.unwomen.org/sites/default/files/Field%20Office%20ESEAsia/Docs/Publications/2017/04/GESIframeworkReportFinal2017compressed.pdf>

Pépin, A., Andriescu, M., Buckingham, S., Mougou, A., Gilloz, O., Collier, N., Tenglerova, H., Dunn, K., Hoya, C., Nájera, L., Nicosiam, D., & Davies, R. (2024). *Impact of gender equality plans across the European Research Area*. Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, European Commission. <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/33fc19b1-74a5-11ef-a8ba-01aa75ed71a1/language-en>

RESET Project. (n.d.). *Gender Equality Survey* [Survey]. RESET. <https://wereset.eu/gender-equality-survey/>

RESET Project. (n.d.). *GIA Checklist*. <https://wereset.eu/gia-checklist/>

UNESCO. (2019). *Gender equality in education: Looking beyond parity*. <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000266145>

UNFPA & Equimundo. (2022, June). *International Men & Gender Equality Survey (IMAGES)*. Retrieved from <https://www.unfpa.org/publications/international-men-gender-equality-survey-images>

United Nations. (n.d.). *Gender-inclusive language*. <https://www.un.org/en/gender-inclusive-language/>

Universidade do Porto. (2025). UP Igualdade: Plano para a Igualdade de Género Universidade do Porto 2025-2028. <https://www.up.pt/portal/documents/1937/UP-Igualdade-Plano-para-a-Igualdade-de-Genero-Universidade-do-Porto-2025-2028.pdf>

7.2. COST Action examples Gender Equality Plans:

Cosmic WISPers. (2024). *Gender Balance Plan* (COST Action CA21106). https://cosmicwispers.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/09/Gender_Balance_Plan_COST_2024.pdf

COST Action CA21101. (2025). *FemCOSY*. <https://cost-cosy.eu/femcosy/>

ENIS Network. (2023). ENIS Gender Inclusion Action Plan 2023 (ENIS COST Action CA20115). https://www.enisnetwork.com/files/ugd/289b04_7e1d6603fe5849a2b511db9fa8d50277.pdf

Marcus, J., Scheibe, S., Gostautaitė, B., Kooij, D., & Sousa, I. C. (2024). *Action Inclusiveness Plan* (COST Action CA22120). <https://leverage-workforce.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/05/COST-Action-LeverAge-Action-Inclusiveness-Plan.pdf>

TREASURE COST Action. (2025, July 13). *Gender Equality and Inclusive Communication Plan* (COST Action CA22114). <https://www.treasurecost.eu/2025/07/13/gender-equality-and-inclusive-communication-plan/>

7.3. Gender Equality Tools:

GEAM tool, explaining how to measure and analyse gender perceptions through surveys and reports, available on the site: <https://gender-ict.net/tools/geam-tool/>

UNESCO. (n.d.). *Gender Equality Tools*: <https://www.unesco.org/en/gender-equality/tools>

European Institute for Gender Equality. (2019). *Gender audit* (MH-02-18-737-EN-N): https://eige.europa.eu/sites/default/files/documents/mh0218737enn_002_0.pdf

Gender Equality in Academia and Research - GEAR tool: <https://eige.europa.eu/gender-mainstreaming/toolkits/gear>

COST recommends the EIGE toolkit on gender-sensitive communication: https://eige.europa.eu/publicationsresources/toolkits-guides/gender-sensitive-communication/first-steps-towards-more-inclusive-language/terms-you-needknow?language_content_entity=en

Annexes / Appendices for the SHiFT Gender Equality Plan (SGEIP)

